

Code Book Subtask 4.3.8 (WP4): Thematic focus analysis of the role of Industry Stakeholders

Aggregate Codes	Meaning	Code Category	Meaning	Illustrative Quotes
1. Understandings of RRI in industry	This category examines how industry stakeholders understand RRI and RRI-related practices, and whether they think that RRI is feasible for industry innovation.	Definitions of responsibility	Situated understandings of responsibility in corporate innovation processes.	Try being an honest steward [...] within the community more broadly I think [...] becomes sort of a core responsibility.
		Irresponsible innovation	Understandings and examples of problematic or irresponsible forms of private sector innovation.	If you're holding something back, or you're misrepresenting it, such that it is not reproducible by the rest of the community, I think you have failed, and I think that's fundamentally irresponsible and dishonest.
		RRI as procedure	Understandings of the steps and stages through which RRI is/can be applied in industry.	When it comes to ethics, our managing director is the one who champions that. He plays a vital role in considering that we are always on top of our game when it comes to considering ethics or any ethic consideration, when you are dealing with clients or customers.
		Upstream RRI	Perceptions and forms of RRI at the level of upstream innovation.	So by having early conversations about what the communities are interested in, they can start to frame their scientific questions. Yes, purely in the interest of knowledge and curiosity, but also gear their outreach plans up front so that they can message properly to the community and get the community to have that kind of buy-in.
		Downstream RRI	Perceptions and forms of RRI at the level of downstream innovation.	In this case, the definition of success as an organisation is to be able to supply safe foods without excess or deficiency, the difficulty is safety for the recipient. The duty here is to supply safe things, and that cannot be achieved without providing a feeling of safety as well.
		RRI in business models	Understandings of the role of RRI ideas in business models	Right now, since I'm working with a lot of energy conflicts and energy issues having to do with challenges and moving toward a lower carbon system, that means I work with people ranging from consumer advocates to utility executives who are absolutely terrified about changing the business model.
		RRI as purpose and aspiration	Perceptions of RRI as an unrealised and possibly unrealisable ideal for industry innovation.	Ethically, I would say that's another third stage that whenever we undertake any project, from the start itself, the aim is to have zero harm and zero discharge to whoever is involved in the project.
		Feasibility of RRI	Understandings of the feasibility of (public sector) RRI in corporate contexts.	So yeah, there are some tangents on about being – what does it mean to be responsible, when the things you're being judged on, maybe don't feel responsible to you in terms of you're being rated – your responsibility is being rated on something where you don't think that makes any sense.

		Alternatives to RRI	Perceptions of alternatives to RRI in industry innovation.	In some cases, from the government perspective, they actually make that illegal.
		Whose responsibility to adopt RRI	Understandings of whose responsibility it is to promote and adopt RRI in corporate innovation.	We are always in the contact with our local ministries and government when they are implementing the legislations because we very often just don't understand how it should sound and the laws or regulations and so on.
		Perspectives on RRI in industry – from outside industry	Perceptions of RRI in industry – as put forward by non-industry stakeholders (e.g. NGOs, etc)	If they [corporations] achieve it, if they meet the needs of their clients, they are also receiving economic gains for this, but [name of the association] does not sell or commercialize anything, we are a non-profit association and what we do is inform, educate and scientifically support the entire theme of crop innovation.
		Disadvantages of RRI	Understandings of the problems and disadvantages that RRI can cause in corporations.	In general, of course overdoing such things [addressing social and ethical issues] could hinder the success of an organization.
2. Role and value of RRI in industry	This category seeks to explore perceptions of the role and value of RRI in private sector innovation contexts.	Perceived benefits of RRI adoption	Perceptions of the value and benefits of RRI adoption in industry innovation	The more you try to involve the local people, give them the jobs, give them the satisfaction of working in a big organization while staying in their own place, the benefit is mutual. Both for them as well as for us, because you get a license to operate, people admire the organization and the local administration also admires the organization.
		Motivations to use RRI	Perceptions of the motivations to promote or adopt RRI in private sector innovation.	The goal of the work was to get safe water to people. Are we achieving that metric? There's lots of other things to measure, but it's that top goal. That's the story we sell to other people to raise funding.
		RRI and SDGs	Perceptions of the role of RRI in realising sustainable development goals (SDGs)	We work with communities to understand what environmental impacts they're feeling most acutely, so in the energy sector, frontline communities, how the climate crisis is impacting them.
		Managing stakeholder relationships	RRI as a means to manage and improve relations with stakeholders, including customers	There are some organizations that choose to, for example, financially sponsor work. There's some organizations that actually donate developer time. So they'll have engineers on their team and say, "Okay. For some number of hours per week, we expect you to do development on GNU Radio and push those contributions back to the community because contributing to the community benefits us fundamentally."
		Understand perceptions of customers	RRI as a form of marketing research, that generates knowledge about consumers.	The general idea is that you make the world better for people and for the clients as well. When you make a solution that actually is being actively used by the clients and in addition to that it brings value to people, it's good for the society, that is very important. I'm certain that big companies have these missions anyway.

		Address societal concerns	RRI as a means to identify and address societal concerns.	As a particular feature of our company, when we provide technology and our customers use that technology, we are interested in them using it appropriately. We understand how to use it correctly, but we have been thinking about whether and how we must improve our efforts to ensure that our customers only use it appropriately.
		Understanding environmental impacts	RRI as a means to identify and address environmental issues.	Within sustainability, we want to ensure that we take care of the safety, the environment, the HSE, health, safety, and environment. Also, the participation of both genders and the community.
		Preventing adverse effects	RRI as a means to identify and prevent adverse effects of technoscientific innovation.	I think for particularly for government use of AI software, this is really key to really think of possible unintended consequences because we know so many cases where I'm pretty sure if this would have done before and if people who are later affected by the use of technology would have been involved in this assessment, they would have anticipated a lot of the bad things that happened much later.
		Prevent dual use and misuse	RRI as a means to identify and prevent dual use or misuse of technoscientific innovations.	Entrepreneurs make sure that they are not used for illegal purposes and things like that, but to expect that they focus on creating and creating and only for this and that purpose... they just don't have the power for that, when they create a new technology, say, a tracking technology, they do not know exactly whether it will be used by someone for bad or good purposes.
		RRI as ethics washing	RRI as a means of public image management and to legitimize controversial practices or technology applications.	It's political ethics-washing, isn't it? I wonder about the ethics of those waving the flag in opposition, and what they knew or didn't know.
3. Dimensions and practices of RRI in industry contexts	Seeks to understand the different dimensions and practices of RRI in private sector innovation, and how, whether and in which ways these relate to the AREA, AIRR and RRI Keys frameworks. Central aims here are (i) to understand how RRI-related ideas are operationalised and put into practice, and	Anticipation	Practices associated with anticipation and foresight in industry innovation.	I don't think it's possible to really grasp the full breadth of what you're doing in terms of what it might enable in the future. It's kind of asking back in the '60s, if somebody said, "What's the impact computers are going have?" It's kind of similar, right?
		Reflectivity	Practices associated with reflectivity in industry innovation.	I think that your comment about how we don't think about what we have done is very characteristic of the company, something that people say about SEG and it's real. We don't reflect much about what we do, that's why, partly, we created the innovation manager position, because someone from outside came to analyse it, otherwise it would have probably stayed as it was.
		Public engagement	Practices associated with public engagement and stakeholder	Socially, I would say, that it comes as a second leg of what we do once an innovation project, or for that matter, any project, is undertaken. We always ensure the involvement

<p>(ii) to identify differences or “gaps” between how RRI has been defined in the public research sector in the UK and EU, and the ways in which ideas of responsibility and responsible innovation are conceptualised in industry settings and different world regions.</p>		deliberation in industry.	of the local community. That’s when the social angle comes into place.
	Inclusion in industry innovation	Practices associated with the promotion of inclusion and equal opportunities in industry.	If your organization, if your company is able to promote culture of sharing and inclusiveness, here in Malawi, people will be very happy or are willing to work with you. They value openness, apart from the privacy as another thing that they value most, but openness is another one.
	Gender	Perceptions of gender dimensions in innovation and practices to address gender inequalities.	I think that the whole debate of equality or equity, or if you have women in the team, the same amount of number, but the boys have been educated to always speak up and be dominant, and the girls always, or have been educated to be more emotional and sensitive and quiet. Of course, they’re not going to give the same input as the guys who have been taught to do so.
	Diversity	Perceptions of issues related to diversity in innovation and practices to promote diversity.	But I wouldn’t say that there is much focus on these people, on diversity, and so on. Attempts are there, but how to expand them is already a matter of governments, I think, or of state, you can’t put too much pressure on business because they already have problems how to create those new, neat and good technologies, not speaking about all the other things, but of course, efforts have to be made.
	Ethics	Practices associated with ethics, ethicality and ethics management in industry.	So making sure that as a community of scientists, there’s some consensus about how the study is done and whether there might be any inadvertent issues with ethics or dealing with particular communities.
	Science communication and public outreach	Practices associated with science communication and outreach in industry	I think that the only perception that I think is problematic specifically for us, is because we are positioned as a bipartisan organization. And the political climate forces you to do extraordinary outreach to conservatively leaning views, just to seem fair.
	RRI training	Opinions, ideas and practices associated with RRI training in private sector contexts.	In the private sector, as much as people really try to actively work on it [taking into account future implications] as a continuous model, just by nature of there not being sufficient people or maybe there’s just not enough training around doing strategic planning, it again tends to be a very rushed process.
	Access to new innovations or products	Practices and ideas related to the promotion of broad access to new products and services.	In terms of like you said, by setting a price at a certain level, you automatically limit or prohibit access to people below a certain income level. And is that a good thing, is that a just thing? Probably not.
	Innovation governance	RRI-related practices that inform the governance of innovation	In general, of course, it’s a very good idea to involve as much as possible stakeholders like the general public and whoever, or people from NGOs or people from

			processes in industry.	companies and people from academia.
		Open access and data sharing	Practices and ideas related to the promotion of open access and data sharing.	That if you conduct research, and your representation of it, or publication of it, precludes reproducibility, because you're not sharing code, or you're not sharing data, you're not sharing process, right?
		Transparency	Practices and ideas related to the promotion and feasibility of transparency in industry.	If a company is not transparent, obviously you lose trust from your customers or customer base. You might have a project or you might have business with them, after doing that business they might not call you back, they might not give you another business, they might not give you another project. It's all about trust between the two parties, customer and client, so they will lose trust if you're not open.
4. Science, technology and innovation (STI) areas in which RRI is employed	This category seeks to identify the different STI areas in which RRI is employed, and to what extent and why there is variation between different areas.	ICT	RRI practices and principles employed in different areas of the ICT innovation domain.	In April, a document called "Int_Corp Group AI and human rights policy" was published, aimed at external communication. This seeks to define the points where we must be careful in carrying out our business activities with respect to AI in particular, including but not limited to AI for biometrics. Of course, privacy is in there, but not only that, fairness and transparency and appropriate use are in there, guidelines for the way we should proceed, are all in there.
		Energy	RRI practices and principles in different areas of the energy innovation domain.	One of NRDC's highest priorities, is trying to address the historical concentration of environmental – particularly energy sector – pollution in communities of color. And to do that, we have to work closely with those communities and really understand what their priorities are, what impacts they're experiencing, and how they're experiencing them on a regular basis.
		Bio-economy	RRI practices and principles in different areas of the bio-economy innovation domain.	In general, the bioeconomy, if we see it globally, I think is the awareness of everyone to exercise their role and how they have to play a role within a community, trying to mimic the biological wisdom and relationships between all the components of a community. In that sense, knowledge, I repeat, I think has to serve the well-being of all, not only humans but also the environment.
		Waste management	RRI practices and principles in different areas of the waste management innovation domain.	Then innovation is a part of the entire move of creating value from waste. Obviously, it imbibes part of sustainability, but innovation is there in all processes also, even in office documentation processes that we would be very happy to have innovation and some projects are done like that also. It has nothing to do with sustainability as such, but then yes, it also becomes a part of that. It's ingrained in the innovation.

5. Key players in (industry) RRI	This category seeks to identify the key players in industry-related forms of RRI.	Multinational corporations	The role and activities of multinationals in enabling or preventing RRI in industry innovation.	In the US that just – oh my goodness. It would have to be Exxon or Mobil doing this instead of the state-owned system, even though it might be done better by the state-owned system.
		Large national corporations	The role and activities of large national firms in enabling or preventing RRI in industry innovation.	It was very interesting to me that the norms in the US are different [than in Sweden], in that, we almost have a – it's almost a religious belief in the sacredness of private enterprise and the private sector. And so, even when something can be done in a way that [...] is more responsible and more accepted by members of the <i>demos</i> , [...] we still feel that we need to find some way to bring the private sector in.
		Small to mid-size firms	The role and activities of national SMEs in enabling or preventing RRI in industry innovation.	For us, success means first of all, the technology that we develop is actually used for beneficial purpose that together with our clients, we finally, let's say, develop [...] solutions that really make a difference for the society because we are this innovation and change oriented. That's one point of the success. [...] Our employees would feel joy with that because that's why they come to work for us, for a small company, but they want to make a change during the day to day job. Of course, another thing is we are still a business so if all of that ends up in the profitable growth of the company.
		Industry associations	The role and activities of industry associations and corporate lobby groups in enabling or preventing RRI in industry innovation.	And so, very often, a lot of these people who have a lot of relationships with the federal body, they might have lobbyists, they have separate trade associations that represent them. And a lot of the times the public doesn't have that type of agency, so they just don't have those types of relationships.
		Universities	The role and activities of universities in enabling or preventing RRI in industry innovation.	Even with the university I'm working with now, I have challenged them, even with the funder in the room, to say a lot of the research you're doing, you get your Master's, you get your PhD, it doesn't do anything for my country. That to me is unethical. It has to lead to something. It has to lead to either improvements in service delivery, it has to lead to change in policy, it has to lead to something tangible for my country, because we are developing country.
		Public-private collaborations	The role and activities of public-private collaborations in the realisation of RRI in industry.	We've gotten funding and support from oil and gas companies looking for research and solutions. There's a local and state-based incubator, accelerator, local support organizations that we've gotten funding through. So in those avenues, we've dealt with the personnel, whoever the point of contact is in those organizations.
		National or local NGOs	The role and activities of national/local NGOs in	What we [a non-profit association] do is inform, educate and scientifically support the entire theme of crop innovation.

			enabling or preventing RRI in industry innovation.	
		Government bodies (e.g. regulatory authorities)	The role and activities of state governments in enabling or preventing RRI in industry innovation.	Especially when the regulatory bodies post notices of proposed rulemaking, that is usually a time when several – whether it's public interest groups, also industry and sometimes you have individuals, like public citizens, who are just very interested in the issue, so they would rally around to actually file public comments in a docket.
		Activist groups	The role and activities of activist groups in in the realisation of RRI in industry.	When there was a lot of movement around the FCC regulating their jurisdiction over the internet and essentially eliminating net neutrality rules and removing the 2015 open internet order, you found that a ton of people, it wasn't just the direct engagement with the federal body. It was also awareness campaigns to make sure that, even the public, reaching into communities, to make sure that they understood what does that mean in the general landscape for just our overall ecosystem, and how that would affect them at least here in the US.
		Customer organisations	The role and activities of customer organisations in the realisation of RRI in industry	In the US, for instance, you have this anti-GMO lobby as you have probably at all places on the planet, but apparently, their view was overruled to have this decision.
		International NGOs	The role and activities of international NGOs in the realisation of RRI in industry.	Here in Europe, [...] the pressure of the consumer and also of the NGOs has made us have a much stricter regulation.
6. Policy Drivers for RRI engagement	This seeks to identify the policy drivers for RRI adoption in industry innovation, and how this differs across countries, political systems and inequalities in wealth and scientific resources.	National policies	The role and effects of national policies in driving the adoption of RRI in private sector innovation.	In terms of getting movement on policy, sometimes you need people who are willing to literally lay in the middle of the street. That's how we got the Americans with Disabilities Act. People literally got out of their wheelchairs and laid in the middle of the street, okay? So that is something that is going to be effective and it gets movement, right? But it took years later for somebody to draft the Americans with Disabilities Act to actually enact it into law.
		International policies	The role and effects of international policies in driving RRI adoption in private sector innovation.	I do not think that it [guidelines for risk assessment of technologies that impact biological diversity] can be so easily manipulated by a single company, honestly, because there are some international standards that are the ones to go to. Then, each country welcomes and adapts these standards to its own situation. I don't think it's so easy that a single company can manipulate this.
		Institutional policies	The role and effects of institutional policies in driving RRI	We were founded in collaboration with US partners, big companies and we work in application of this gene-editing technology for different industries. Which means that our business model is not about

			adoption in industry.	developing a particular treatment method or a drug or a new plant variety. We apply the technology for all these potential applications depending on what is the business of our clients in this form.
		Pressure to adhere to international standards	The role and effects of international standards in driving RRI adoption in private sector innovation.	Colombian specialists have worked with the United Nations to establish other biosafety systems in other countries. In all countries where GM crops are present, there are instituted regulatory systems, some better established than others, but in all of them there are protocols, international standards, which embrace the Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety.
		Participation in International collaborations	The role and effects of international collaborations in driving RRI adoption of RRI in firms.	Regarding stakeholders from the government, it's more like collaboration for the development of the whole biotech industry in Lithuania. We really help them to understand, let's say, foreign markets or how the industry is working or helping with the context to attract some foreign companies here.
		Access to markets in multiple countries	The role and effects of aspirations to access multiple markets in driving RRI adoption in firms.	But when we work with the clients or at these potential clients from different countries we have some contact with Asia too so we have to know how these technologies are perceived there and if there would be any market there at all.
		Corporate self-governance	Lack of policy or regulatory vacuum – triggering forms of corporate self-governance	If there are no set rules by either the government or universities themselves, then you're asking the researchers themselves to do this moral unethical assessment, which I find tricky. Of course, we all have our own definitions and values.
		Public debate	Public debate as a driver for government or institutional policies that promote RRI-related ideas.	Like in Germany, they have been testing this and there's a very active debate right now on the use of facial recognition through police agencies. We've seen many statements by public officials that clearly show that they do not understand how the technology works and the impact that it can have. This is very dangerous if you have people who make these decisions and they don't know about the risks and the functioning of the systems.
7. Challenges to RRI adoption in industry	This category seeks to identify and understand some of the central challenges to the adoption of RRI ideas and policies in industrial innovation contexts	Limitations of public sector RRI in industry	Tensions that arise between public sector RRI and the characteristics & needs of industry innovation.	I see benefit in it (RRI), of course. Again, if you have a very strong framework of the boundaries of how to use the technology, it could work. Then again, in certain African countries, why are people there suffering a lot, and how is it possible that other people have access to food in a very excessive way?
		Costs of RRI	The financial aspects of RRI adoption, and whether RRI is seen as profitable and worthwhile.	I do consider it, but I can't afford the cost. Beyond that, we believe that the more important things should be to ensure food safety and ensure Japan's national interest.

		Lack of understanding of RRI	Lack of understanding among corporate staff of what RRI is, why it is of value.	The first thing we strive to do is to understand the values, the social concepts and all the underlying important elements that would add value to the work that we are doing. So, we have to understand that and make sure that that is not just understood by one person but the entire team doing the research or involved in the research has that understanding and that we are able to comfortably appreciate as well as approach the people with that particular understanding.
		Lack of knowledge on how to do RRI	Lack of understanding among corporate staff on how to apply RRI ideas in industry settings.	We're relying a lot on individuals' experience to define whether, "Hey, is this affecting other people or is this going to have an unintentional effect that we have no measure for?" That's purely just going on experience and thoughts of the individuals that are signing off, which is unfortunate, but I actually don't have a good way of improving that norm to create a more objective evaluation of who and how much it's affecting the unintended populations.
		Uncertainties about who should do RRI	Uncertainties about who is responsible to promote, finance and implement RRI.	Basically, [...] the message needs to come from the top that companies exist in society and need to address social and ethical issues. It is important that top managers properly transmit this message. You have to create desirable values from top to bottom.
		Value of RRI for corporations not clear	Lack of understanding of the potential value and benefits of RRI adoption in corporate settings.	For instance, I read an article from some people from the plant sciences saying that perhaps if this responsible innovation, so reaching out, trying to anticipate consequences, which is something that they were doing anyway, is implemented, this could avoid the regulation that has been implemented, and therefore this would give the competitive advantage of them as a research group that have been working.
		Need for secrecy in industry innovation	Tensions between demands for open access and transparency and the need for secrecy in firms.	Business secrets can become a big hurdle for this type of accountability. We've seen this in so many cases, unfortunately.
		Economic incentives override RRI	Economic incentives and priorities weigh stronger than a commitment to ethics and RRI.	There are some restrictions on who can use it [digital tracking systems], to whom those products can be sold, but it is in the nature of an entrepreneur to sell them to anyone, they still need to be educated. I don't know to what extent education could help here.
		Insufficient support from management	RRI adoption is insufficiently supported at the higher management level in firms.	It depends on management. Everything depends on proper management and that, again, the whole society has to be aware that a monoculture is the most risky thing it can do. This has nothing to do with GM but with agricultural practices.

		Challenges to operationalise and implement RRI	Corporate staff find it difficult to operationalise and implement RRI ideas in industry innovation.	. The law is provided, which must be provided, but the implementation is not carried out. That is a problem. It is no use placing biometric aspects if the integration has not been done first.
		Insufficient support from the government	Challenges arising from insufficient support to promote RRI ideas by national (or regional) government administrations.	Did the administration value, or want to support, some of the things that you're asking for? Do they lean towards corporate interests or public interest? And things like that. But there are lots of things that I feel like factor into that. But right now, it's not necessarily that there's some sort of marker in terms of – I feel a little bit like some of this changes all the time, just based on who is the – I don't want to say. I'm trying to avoid talking about the administration. But this administration is not necessarily supportive of some of these goals, and it would be very different if it were a different administration, that's all.
8. Challenges to RRI adoption in a diverse global environment	This category seeks to understand key challenges to the adoption of RRI in industry in a diverse global landscape, that is characterised by cultural, social and political heterogeneity, as well as unequal distribution of wealth, resources, social security and health care.	Governments do not support RRI	Lack of support and/or different priorities results in insufficient government support for RRI adoption.	If you have governments deregulating, that does not seem like something that erects a barrier between the general public being able to actually weigh in on proposals. However, implicitly, as you deregulate, the inertia of larger organizations or larger industry players having power essentially makes it more difficult for the public to engage.
		Economic priorities outweigh concern with RRI	Economic priorities and demands for rapid development are more important than a systematic concern with ethics and RRI.	I do think it [RRI] would benefit society, but only if it's done on the global scale. Because then also European companies would be like, "Okay, I cannot do it here, then maybe I need to branch in, I don't know, Brazil and Namibia". Then they would go there to stay competitive, which, of course, they have to survive.
		RRI as undermining competitiveness	RRI and ethics are seen as hindering effective innovation and undermining (international or interfirm) competitiveness.	I think if we would put these legislations and frameworks in place, it would slow us down as the European Union or the Netherlands, definitely, and maybe we couldn't explore in all the areas we would like to.
		Secretive innovation	Challenges for the adoption of RRI due to the secretive nature of military innovation.	The two most primary being things that are considered trade secrets and not wanting to reveal something that could be secret sauce that enables – especially DeepSig for example.
		Lack of infrastructures and resources	Lack of financial resources as well as regulatory infrastructures prevent effective adoption of RRI.	Lack of accountability within the sector where people install systems that are poorly installed but nobody holds them accountable. In the UK, you know how it is. If you were to put a bad drug on the market that kills people, you will be taken to task. But in Malawi, you can draw a bad well that is not drilled to government standards, nothing happens. Those are some of the gaps.

		Different political systems	Non-democratic contexts prevent RRI and public dialogue.	Going back to the example of privacy, if somebody's developing something and they think it might lead to the ability to track a user, for example, it's really more of a – instead of a well-intentioned policy, it's really more of a concern about abuse by very negative policies, I would say. So it would be a concern, for example, about an authoritarian state using some part of the work to suppress dissidents, right? That is a concern in wireless, right. An authoritarian state using technology to track people using their cellphones, for example. It's the same kind of thing you get, same kind of concerns you might have, for example, with facial recognition technology and machine learning.
		Diverse understandings of ethics & responsibility	Challenges to RRI adoption that arise from cultural and social heterogeneity.	I am very much against the idea of research for research's sake. This is the ethical part. In the context of a developing country like Malawi, I don't think we have the luxury of research for research's sake. I think research that is developed has to lead to some development agenda, or to lead to some improvement in practice, or to at least inform better policy. It has to lead to something. I get requests from students all the time from other countries asking to come and do research. The question I always ask is, what is this going to lead to?
		Lack of trust	Challenges to RRI adoption that arise from a lack of trust in government, science, corporations or other institutions or stakeholders	Right now, because of the issue of lack of trust in government systems, most of that money is coming through NGOs. It would be the case for the foreseeable future. It is very different if you go to Uganda where most of the donor funding goes through the government and NGOs have to apply for money from the government if they want to do anything.